

**LATEST RESULTS FROM THE ~~LEGEND~~ EXPERIMENT ON
THE SEARCH FOR NEUTRINOLESS $\beta\beta$ DECAY**

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NuPhys2026 • King's College London • 7 Jan 2026

$$(A, Z) \longmapsto (A, Z+2) + 2e^- + 2\cancel{\nu_e}$$

“The search for $0\nu\beta\beta$ decay is one of the most compelling and exciting challenges in all of contemporary physics”¹

- $0\nu\beta\beta$ observation \Rightarrow Majorana neutrino and Lepton Number Violation
- Lepton number \leftrightarrow Barion number \mapsto new physics, baryogenesis?

Light neutrino mass mechanism

The (Majorana) neutrino that mediates $0\nu\beta\beta$ is the one that oscillates and the Standard Model is an effective theory (*seesaw mechanism*)

$$(T_{1/2}^{0\nu})^{-1} = G^{0\nu} |M^{0\nu}|^2 m_{\beta\beta}^2 \quad \text{Majorana effective mass}$$

¹100+ papers per year with “ $0\nu\beta\beta$ ” in the title [INSPIRE-HEP statistics]

SEARCHING FOR $0\nu\beta\beta$ WITH GERMANIUM: CONCEPT

High-Purity Germanium detectors enriched in ^{76}Ge

- source = detector \rightarrow high efficiency
- pure \rightarrow low intrinsic background
- Ge crystal \rightarrow outstanding energy resolution
- charge drift in E-field \rightarrow topological discrimination

SIGNAL-LIKE

MULTIPLICITY CUT

PULSE-SHAPE
DISCRIMINATION

ARGON ANTI-
COINCIDENCE

“The collaboration aims to develop a **phased, ^{76}Ge -based** double-beta decay experimental program with discovery potential at a **half-life beyond 10^{28} yr**, using existing resources as appropriate to expedite physics results.”

LEGEND-200

- 200 kg of $^{\text{enr}}\text{Ge}$ ($\times 5$ yr), in GERDA cryostat
- Operating with 140 kg of $^{\text{enr}}\text{Ge}$
- $B \sim 2 \cdot 10^{-4}$ cts / (keV kg yr) $\mapsto T_{1/2}^{0\nu} > 10^{27}$ yr

LEGEND-1000

arXiv 2107.11462

“pre-conceptual design report”

- 1 ton of $^{\text{enr}}\text{Ge}$ ($\times 10$ yr), awaiting funding
- $B < 10^{-5}$ cts / (keV kg yr) $\mapsto T_{1/2}^{0\nu} > 10^{28}$ yr
- Cover full $m_{\beta\beta}$ inverted ordering region

THE FIRST CONFIGURATION OF LEGEND₋₂₀₀

Hardware status until 2024 — see talk at [TAUP23]

- Installed first **142 kg** of HPGe detectors (Oct '22)
- 130 kg operational (12 kg OFF due to hardware issues)

THE LEGEND -200 COMMISSIONING

Exposure accumulated over 1 year valid for:

- Background and performance characterization data set: 76.2 kg yr
 - plus 10.2 kg yr of special “background characterization” runs
- $0\nu\beta\beta$ data set: 61 kg yr
 - includes only data with fully vetted Pulse Shape Discrimination (PSD) parameters

- $\sim 0.1\%$ FWHM at $Q_{\beta\beta}$
 - including large inverted-coaxial detectors
- **Stable** energy observables
 - monitored with weekly ^{228}Th calibrations
- Second-order variations **tracked in time**
 - data set partitioned according to stability

- **Blinding** applied at $Q_{\beta\beta} = 2039$ keV (50 keV window)
- 95–99% survival of physical events after **data cleaning** at $Q_{\beta\beta}$
- **Multiplicity cut** rejects 26% of events at $Q_{\beta\beta}$, 2 events removed by **Muon Veto**

Pulse shape classifier: $A/E = \max(\text{current}) / \text{energy}$

- Strong suppression of surface α and β (^{42}K) events
- ~60% suppression of Compton multi-site events at $Q_{\beta\beta}$
- $0\nu\beta\beta$ survival fraction of ~85%

- **Improved light yield** compared to GERDA ($\times 3$)
- **Stable** argon properties
 - *Monitoring through LLAMA instrumentation*
- **Characterized** with special calibration runs
 - *~ 1 photoelectron per 10 keV deposited in argon*
- **Strong suppression** of background above $2\nu\beta\beta$
 - *$\beta\beta$ decay signal acceptance of $\sim 93\%$*

- Events rejected if SiPM signal in coincidence with HPGe signal
- Strong **suppression of background on top of $2\nu\beta\beta$**
- $\beta\beta$ decay signal acceptance of $\sim 93\%$

- Strong **anti-correlation** of argon and PSD cuts
- Overall $0\nu\beta\beta$ survival fraction of $\sim 60\%$
- “Pure” $2\nu\beta\beta$ distribution, few events surviving at $Q_{\beta\beta}$

Germanium exposure:

- 61 kg yr unblinded between 2024 and 2025
 - 38.1 kg yr from flagship detectors (*Inverted Coaxial*)

Background index:

- 48.3 kg yr unblinded in 2024: $0.5^{+0.3}_{-0.2}$ cts / (keV tonne yr)
 - *highest-performing detectors*
- extra 12.8 kg yr unblinded in 2025: $1.3^{+0.8}_{-0.5}$ cts / (keV tonne yr)
 - *detectors known to have worse performance*
- **Quasi-background-free!**
 - *i.e. less than one background count expected in the data set*
- Background compatible with GERDA but we are working on reducing it!

GERDA (127 kg yr), **MAJORANA DEMONSTRATOR** (65 kg yr) and **LEGEND** (61 kg yr) **combined** $0\nu\beta\beta$ fit

- p -value of background-only = 29%
- $T_{1/2}^{0\nu}$ lower limits (90% frequentist C.L.)

Observed	Sensitivity
$> 1.9 \cdot 10^{26}$ yr	$2.8 \cdot 10^{26}$ yr

- Majorana effective mass upper limits (90% C.L.): $m_{\beta\beta} < \underline{70 - 200}$ meV

*phenomenological
NME range*

LEGEND-200 contribution

- +30% of limit median expectation
- event at 1.3σ from $Q_{\beta\beta}$ weakens combined limit

- Paper to appear on *Phys. Rev. Lett.* in the next few days!
- **Restarted data taking with an improved configuration**
 - *new radioassay campaign*
 - *improved material cleaning techniques*
 - *repaired/recycled problematic detectors*
- **New:** hints that the background is now lower than before!
 - *working on confirming this in the next months*
- **Now:** focus on **stable data taking** to accumulate exposure for the next unblinding

LEGEND - 1000

- Optimized for $0\nu\beta\beta$ *discovery sensitivity beyond 10^{28} yr*
- Background goal: 10^{-5} cts / (keV kg yr) \mapsto *quasi-background-free* for 10 ton yr exposure
- Has a low-risk path to meeting its goal based on MAJORANA, GERDA and LEGEND-200

THE LEGEND -1000 BASELINE DESIGN AT LNGS

- April 2016** LEGEND collaboration formed
- Dec 2019** Completion of GERDA \mapsto LEGEND-200 commissioning start
- July 2021** DOE Portfolio Review (LEGEND-1000, nEXO, CUPID) [arXiv 2107.11462](https://arxiv.org/abs/2107.11462)
- Sep 2021** North American / European Summit at LNGS: *stakeholders strive for international funding for two ton-scale $0\nu\beta\beta$ experiments, one at SNOLAB and one at LNGS*
- Oct 2021** DOE verbally announced that [LEGEND-1000 emerged as the portfolio review winner in all but one category](#)
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- 2022/2023** Commissioning/physics data taking of LEGEND-200
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- Nov 2025** **New!** *Critical Decision 1*: preliminary reference design, strategize funding
- 2026/27** Start of procurement of long-lead items (Ge, cryostat, infrastructure)
- 2030/31** Commissioning and first data

THANK YOU!

by M. Willers

BACKUP

MODELING DATA BEFORE ANALYSIS CUTS

- Simulations and material radioassay **underpredict** ^{228}Th in physics data
 - *Hard to estimate systematic uncertainty on the assay results*
 - *ICP-MS not predictive if secular equilibrium is broken*
- This background is efficiently **suppressed by analysis cuts**

MODELING DATA BEFORE ANALYSIS CUTS

- Bayesian background model using data before analysis cuts
 - Includes 10.2 kg yr from special “background characterization” runs
- Data well reproduced, model is flat at $Q_{\beta\beta}$
 - No “hotspot” or significant asymmetry observed in data
 - Model can test hypotheses on the origin of ^{228}Th